

Role of Women in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math

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Abstract -Women are increasingly at the forefront of many aspects of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). Women's participation in STEM is a global concern according to UNESCO. As per the data according to UNESCO only 35% of students in higher education worldwide are women. In India, nevertheless, women comprise 43.2% of the sample across UG, PG, and PhD programs. Work culture is shifting and changing that leads to new inventions, groundbreaking scientific discoveries blend art and technology and policies for safe and effective health which can communicate effectively to several audience through scientific findings. However, higher percentage of women stepped in to STEM in comparison with rest of the world with several challenges. Yet men continue to dominate women in all the upper levels of professions. Most of the school students both girls and boys prefer science and math courses as they leave high school and pursue engineering and science as their core subjects in college. In comparison with men, women are much less likely they intend to STEM. Dramatic differences were observed in students, only 20% of women achieving bachelor's degree in science and engineering further declines in the transition to the workplace. McKinsey primary research suggested 40-160 million women globally may need to transition between occupations by 2030, into higher-skilled roles. Further, it is predicted that nearly 12 million Indian women could be staring at job losses owing to automation. Secondary research and interviews with stakeholders highlight gender responsive principles and host of factors that are changing the landscape of employment. Skilling outcomes and sector-specific job creation to fertility rates and family sizes can enable and harness women's workforce participation.

Key Words: UNESCO, STEM, Primary research, Secondary research, Technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) are widely regarded as critical to the national economy. Concern about America's ability to be competitive in the global economy has led to a number of calls to action to strengthen the pipeline into these fields. The most critical issue for the government, educators and industry leaders is developing and expanding the STEM workforce. Due to automation and Artificial intelligence (AI), STEM education enables women to keep up with this transformation by giving them transferable skills. During the past 50 years there was tremendous increase in women participation in education and workforce but the progress has been uneven. Increasing women's participation in STEM could potentially close the gender gap¹ (Fig.1).

Figure: 1. women's participation in STEM

Expanding and developing the STEM workforce is a critical issue for government, industry leaders, and educators. Despite the tremendous gains that girls and women have made in education and the workforce during the past 50 years, progress

has been uneven, and certain scientific and engineering disciplines remain overwhelmingly male. This report addresses why there are still very few women in certain scientific and engineering fields and provides recommendations to increase the number of women in these fields by boosting women’s cumulative earnings². In 2020 the COVID-19 pandemic began has considerably gaining the importance of STEM and technology occupations were drastically expanded and growing approximately 37 per cent and 38 per cent, respectively³. Women who are more employed were take up science and earn about 28 percent more than the women who study non-technical subjects⁴ (Fig.2).

Fig. 2. Representing women in different departments

FEW WOMEN IN STEM

Women are under-represented at Indian research universities in science, technology, engineering and mathematics fields.

STEM education is developing and becoming more important in a daily life from human perspective. They are gaining skills such as experiential learning, pedagogies, logical reasoning, and with the ability to solve complex real life situations⁴. Policy problems such as climate crisis have become a critical component to face. STEM education for women is creating more employment opportunities and also becoming platform to learn technical and scientific skills that can help to create a more balanced environment could fill the gap between men and women⁵ Furthermore, women has become competitor to men as women empowerment in STEM disrupt the poverty in marginalized communities very potentially (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Role of woman in STEM

1.1 STEM Education and Employment

Indian government is currently working on constantly changing and evolving labour market especially in Artificial Intelligence and automation, make women to gain transferable skills and transform the gender gap. Indian women are to be employed more than the women who take up non-technical subjects. 28% of women were employed and earning more who have taken up technical subjects (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Women employment in India

STEM can develop and enhance critical thinking, logical and reasoning skills in women to prove invaluable for individuals to approach problem solving. The participation of women in STEM has become a complex problem to the Indian government while addressing⁶. Hence, the government is working very seriously towards addressing the problem with the GATI (Gender Advancement for Transforming Institutions) charter, which is a voluntary, signatory charter to nudge research institutions to support diversity and inclusion

across 30 pilot institutions), and programs like Vigyaan Jyoti encouraging high-school girls through experiential learning is promising⁷ (Fig.5).

GATI Pilot Journey

Some other recommendations that the brief highlights include:

- Students from beginning at the early primary school level should develop interest towards STEM in girls.
- Encouraging girl child education in science by providing specific provisions such as reservations at IITs.
- Ensure a safe and flexible workplace to women in STEM and mandating charters like GATI.
- Providing opportunities to women into their roles after a break and allow to work again through return ship programs.

Understanding the STEM ecosystem and implementing recommendations and promises to faster economy growth could leads to prosperity of women. Innovation, creativity, and competitiveness retain and attract more women in the STEM workforce.

1.2. Present Scenario of Indian women in STEM

An opportunity to be given to women in diverse fields such as science and technological products, services and solutions are likely to be better designed⁸. Research reports suggest that enrolment and participation of women in education has increased from 19 million to 21 million. 43 per cent of women are registering for several courses such as undergraduate, postgraduate, M.Phil, and Ph.D⁹. This shows 50 per cent of women are undergraduates and more specifically 50 per cent of female registered in Arts and Sciences. However, the percentage of women registered for Bachelors of Technology (B.Tech) and Masters of Technology (M.Tech) is negligible. 3

lakh students enrolled Bachelor of Engineering (B.E.) course of which, only 28.5 per cent are female.¹⁰

1.3. Reasons for low percentage of women in STEM careers in India

- **Discrimination and gender bias:** In contrast to men, women are often discriminated in hiring, promotions, and in workplace. They are treated as less competent in engineering and technical fields and limiting their opportunities.
- **Challenges at workplace:** women have to balance family life and work is a big challenge for women. Flexible work hours, childcare support, maternity benefits support women to work in various STEM fields otherwise leads to dropping out from the workforce. In India many IT companies are yet to adopt gender-sensitive polices that enable women to balance family and work.
- **Facilitators and Mentors:** The absence of women facilitators and mentors create psychological barrier for young women. Proper mentor should guide women in leadership positions within STEM fields. Without mentors, many women feel isolated in male-dominated workplaces.

1.4. Socio-cultural factors influence the student's career and subject choices in India

Women have prioritized to family culture and responsibilities over career. Long working hours and dedication and involvement in STEM fields put pressure on women and also face additional societal pressures discourage women from pursuing STEM careers¹¹. As a result, women's enrolment in some prestigious science subjects, such as chemistry (42 per cent), physics (38 per cent) and engineering (32 per cent), remains relatively low. Research report shows that only 6.7 per cent students at the undergraduate level are enrolled in mechanical engineering and 23 per cent of females in civil engineering, 17 per cent in undergraduate, postgraduate and PhD levels, and some of the female students participation is very low in streams such as mechanical, electrical and civil

engineering, less than 10 percent of female students opted mechanical engineering across all levels⁽¹¹⁾. However, other fields, such as life sciences (56 per cent), microbiology (67 per cent), and information technology/computer sciences (54 per cent), witness higher enrolment of women, as per Ministry of Education (2020)¹⁹ data. Therefore, the women's participation is skewed towards certain fields and even within STEM fields. In terms of employment, a UNESCO report (2022) indicates that the presence of female principal investigators in Research and Development (R&D) projects is abysmal; in 2000, 13 per cent of the samples were women.¹⁰

1.5. What Limits Women's Participation in STEM

Participation of women in STEM is very limited it has become a global issue¹². The different stages of the trends in the STEM sector could be understand using a lifecycle approach. The stages are characterized broadly as entry, experience, retention, and leadership. Despite of small percentage of women are focused in STEM fields, the overall percentage of women in STEM has dramatically increased during the past decades¹³. The education system in India has gaps that can limit women from entering into the STEM ecosystem (Fig.6).

Fig. 6. Education and employment gaps in females

Conclusion

The STEM education system is more expensive and becomes inaccessible to women due to financial investment as they need to spend amount for coaching institutes often expensive and worthwhile investments by most of the household women. In recent decades women had cross the border line and had taken step forward into the STEM workforce. Women's workforce in STEM had gradually increased in various disciplines as well as tenure status. 40 percent of women registered for undergraduate, postgraduate and Doctoral programs in colleges and universities, however, participation and registration of woman in STEM disciplines was significantly less. 22 percent woman as faculty in computer and information sciences, 19 percent of women in math, 18 percent in physical sciences and 12 percent in engineering. Finally women made up only 34 percent as faculty represented lower faculty ranks than in higher ranks among STEM faculty.

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